

Correlation Analysis of Enugu Electricity Distribution Company's Electricity Bill

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, we carried out correlation analysis to analyze the expenditure made by the users of electricity and the actual quantity of electricity their given amount of money can buy for them. We observed from the study that electricity users spent more money to get the same value (quantity of electricity), and the relationship between these two variables are inversely related with correlation coefficient of $\rho_{1,2} = -0.02134$. That means that as one is increasing, the other is decreasing. The effect of this is so drastic and a reflection of what Nigerians face generally in the other sectors of the economy. From the study, we also found that tariff rate and value added tax is inversely related to quantity of electricity. This means that both tax and VAT deplete the quantity of electricity that is bought by the consumers. The only variables that have direct relationship with each other are tariff rate and value added tax. Both of them move in the same direction. The overall effect of these relationship points to the fact that people spent more money in Nigeria now to get the same value they used to get before. Hence, the cost of living is high and increasing while the standard of living is falling and inflation is at alarming rate.

1. INTRODUCTION

Electricity all over the world is known for its importance in industrial development, household supply of energy, economic growth and development; aid in doing various businesses, help immensely in electronic dependent works and businesses, and contributes to the GDP of a country. The importance of electricity to human lives cannot be over stressed and for this reason, any country that wants to be industrialized must take constant supply of electricity as a priority. In Nigeria, electricity supply has been a problem from one administration to another. The amount of public fund invested in the power sector starting from 1999 when the country returned from military rule to democracy and up to date was enormous and yet the problem of electricity persisted.

Nigeria has severally changed her policies on electricity with corresponding change in nomenclatures. Prior to 1999, the name was NEPA (National Electric Power Authority) and it was changed to PHCN (Power Holding Company of Nigeria) after the return of democracy with some innovations; huge investment to stabilize the electricity sector and enhance electricity supply. In some few years ago, the government of Nigeria succeeded in privatizing the power sector. The privatization was based on the geopolitical zones of the country. Our interest in this paper is on the South East geopolitical zone of Nigeria. In the South East, the name of the electricity distribution company is called EEDC Plc (Enugu Electricity Distribution Company). EEDC - one of the distribution companies (DISCOs) - buys some quantity of electricity from electricity generating companies (GENCOs). GENCOs are made up of public and private electricity generating companies regulated by NERC (National Electricity Regulatory Commission). The sole purpose of these DISCOs is to provide electricity to companies, industries, businesses, households etc, and make profit as business enterprise. Generally, EEDC operate at a loss because of her inability to track non customers who use the electricity. For this reason, her customers are made to pay for the electricity used by the noncustomers through the charge of higher electricity bill. This higher bill is passed to those customers whose bio-data are in the data base of EEDC.

EEDC Plc engages in electricity distribution in the South Eastern part of Nigeria. The company is based in Enugu capital city, Enugu State Nigeria. EEDC Plc is a subsidiary of Power Holding Company of Nigeria (PHCN). On September 11, 2013, Enugu Electricity Distribution Plc was commissioned to operate as a subsidiary of Interstate Electrics Limited. It was fully owned and funded by the Nigerian Government until November 1st, 2013 when it was acquired by Interstate Electricity Limited following the Privatization of the power sector by the Federal Government of Nigeria. The company distributes electricity across the five south eastern states, namely; Abia, Anambra, Imo,

Enugu and Ebonyi States. The geographical area covered by EEDC is about 30,000km² and EEDC's Business operations are managed by 18 Business Districts (BD) and 148 service centers spread across the five south east states. The service centers are managed by a feeder manager while the districts are managed by district managers who reports to the corporate headquarters in Enugu. The census population of this geographical area is estimated to be about twenty-one million (21,000,000) in 2018. However, EEDC's customer population is about 800,000 revealing a huge gap or variance between census population and customer population for the distribution company. This gives a ration of 1:26, meaning that every one customer of EEDC has twenty-six dependents. Put differently, in every twenty-six persons using electricity in the geographical area, there is only one customer of EEDC that pays for electricity bill. This makes it practically impossible for the distribution company to breakeven, and this has posed a lot of challenges to EEDC in particular and other distribution companies (DISCOs) in Nigeria. The main problem facing Electricity Distribution Companies in Nigeria is high Aggregate Technical, Commercial and Collection (ATC&C) losses. The ATC&C loss of EEDC stood at 63.38% of total revenue received as at November, 2018 compared to all other Nigeria DISCOs average loss of 49.15%. This loss is the difference between the amount of electricity received by a distribution company from the transmission company and the amount of electricity for which it issued invoices to her customers plus the adjusted collection loss. The aggregation of the losses is a technique for assessing the overall performance of a utility company (EEDC). This ATC&C loss is estimated to be about 24 billion naira yearly and has been accumulating since the takeover of the electricity distribution company by EEDC in 2013, Anyalewechi (2018).

It is obvious, in order to survive in the business where the estimated majority of electricity users are not paying the monthly electricity bills, EEDC introduces a higher tariff rate compared to other DISCOs in Nigeria and this is affecting the real customers. And since the same tariff rate applies to different states under EEDC, the researchers restricted themselves to Enugu districts for the study. The study concentrates on those who use pre-paid meters to determine their electricity bills. Electricity bill (a kind of printed receipt for electricity purchased by customers) comprise of four variables stated in the bill namely; the energy sum measured in naira, the energy measured in kwh, the tariff rate measured in naira and the value added tax (VAT) measured in naira. These variables keep changing to reflect the economic situation of the country. And we want to see how these variables (variates) correlate with one another and the economic lives of Nigerians using EEDC Plc as a case study.

Hence, correlation is the measure of the extent of relationship among variables, where both dependent

and independent variables are random. Since we have multiple variables of interest called variates, we applied an aspect of multivariate analysis to determine the nature of relationship that exists among the variates. This paper is aimed at applying correlation analysis to determine the degree and nature of relationship among the variates (the energy sum (₦), quantity of electricity (kwh), tariff rate (₦) and value added tax (VAT) (₦)). The paper is divided into five sections as follows: In section one; we give the general introduction of the work. Section two was devoted to literature review. In section three, we treated materials and methods. In section four, we implemented the developed model and finally, in section five, we treated results and discussions.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

We want to determine the relationship between the expenditure on electricity, the quantity of energy (kwh), the tariff rate, value added tax (VAT) and their impact on the customers. The cost of living would compare with the minimum expenditure necessary to maintain the representative consumer at the same level of well-being at different time periods or sets of prices, William (1999). But this is slightly different because it is concerned with the extent of the relationship and the direction of the relationship among the variates. This will help to determine the cost; standard of living and inflation in the electricity sector on one hand and the economy at large.

The analytical framework for cost-of-living measurement is based on the assumption that a household is trying to achieve the highest possible standard of living while staying within its budget Dale and Daniel (1999). All common articles of consumption had fixed prices which often did not change for a lifetime, and if any dealer had attempted to charge more than custom demanded, it would have attracted the attention and aroused the indignation of the whole community, Alan (2007). These conditions have been so altered today that a merchant like EEDC has the monopoly of electricity supply in the south eastern part of Nigeria and can charge their customers whatever they like at any given time as electricity bills.

Properly measuring inflation is an essential ingredient in economic policy making, setting optimal contracts, guiding monetary policy, and determining the financing needs of all levels of government. In trying to do this, some errors are incurred, but increasing sample size not only will reduce bias, but also will eliminate the variance effects of sampling error, Ralph (2007). Inflation plays a central role in economic policymaking, as well as influencing decisions made by individuals. Consumers, economists, and policymaker's commonly use the consumer price index (CPI) as a measure of inflation. However, critics have suggested that several

sources of bias in the CPI result in an overestimate of changes in the cost of living, Denise and Hill (2003). What actually happened was that biases were not initially considered before constructing various CPI's and hence, a heavy presence of bias that leads to over or under estimation of inflation. In this study, inflation and cost of living are relative and not pronounced. But the nature of the relationship among the variates will indicate the economic status of the general consumers of electricity in Nigeria.

3. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The variables of interest in this study are the Energy sum (₦) (that is expenditure on electricity), energy (kwh) (that is, the quantity of electricity a specific money can buy), tariff rate (₦) and value added tax (VAT) (₦). Each of the variates are represented by X_i , $i = 1, \dots, 4$, and each of the variates dependent of the other, Arua et al (2000), Amuji et al (2022).

Assumption:

The following are the assumption that must be satisfies before we apply correlation analysis on the EEDC data:

1. The data (variates) are dependent on one another
2. $-1 \leq \rho_{ij} \leq 1$; the correlation coefficient lies between minus one and plus one
3. $\rho_{ij} = 0$; implies that there is no relationship between the variables i and j .
4. $\rho_{ij} = 1$; perfect positive correlation
5. $\rho_{ij} = -1$; perfect negative correlation

The closer the correlation coefficient gets to one the stronger the relationship and the more it gets closer to zero the weaker the relationship. A correlation coefficient with positive value has a direct relationship between the variables while a negative value indicate an inverse relationship. These relationships among the variates correlate with the economic status of the customers, that use the electricity. Correlation coefficient is a dimensionless quantity and therefore has no unit of measurement.

Multivariate data are data collected on several dimensions or characteristics of the same individual or item or experimental trial, Onyeagu (2003). In this paper, we are interested in four variates namely; Energy sum (₦) represented by the random variable (X_1), energy (kwh) represented by (X_2), tariff rate (₦) represented by (X_3) and value added tax (VAT) (₦) represented by (X_4). These are multivariate data from the EEDC electricity bill considered in this paper. The data was collected from customer's electricity bills over

a period of six years, 2016 to 2021. We applied multivariate analysis since we are considering many dependent variables at the same time and their effects

compared simultaneously, multivariate analysis provide the best model for such a problem.

Layout of dispersion matrix for the samples

$$(n_i - 1)S_i^2 = \begin{bmatrix} X_{11} & X_{12} & X_{13} & X_{14} \\ X_{21} & X_{22} & X_{23} & X_{24} \\ X_{31} & X_{32} & X_{33} & X_{34} \\ X_{41} & X_{42} & X_{43} & X_{44} \end{bmatrix}$$

Where the variances are:

$$X_{11} = \sum_1^{27} X_1^2 - n\bar{X}_1^2; \quad X_{22} = \sum_1^{21} X_2^2 - n\bar{X}_2^2; \quad X_{33} = \sum_1^{27} X_3^2 - n\bar{X}_3^2; \quad X_{44} = \sum_1^{27} X_4^2 - n\bar{X}_4^2;$$

and covariance are:

$$X_{12} = \sum_{X_1=1}^{27} \sum_{X_2=1}^{27} X_1 X_2 - n\bar{X}_1 \bar{X}_2; \quad X_{13} = \sum_{X_1=1}^{27} \sum_{X_3=1}^{27} X_1 X_3 - n\bar{X}_1 \bar{X}_3; \quad X_{14} = \sum_{X_1=1}^{27} \sum_{X_4=1}^{27} X_1 X_4 - n\bar{X}_1 \bar{X}_4;$$

$$X_{23} = \sum_{X_2=1}^{27} \sum_{X_3=1}^{27} X_2 X_3 - n\bar{X}_2 \bar{X}_3; \quad X_{24} = \sum_{X_2=1}^{27} \sum_{X_4=1}^{27} X_2 X_4 - n\bar{X}_2 \bar{X}_4; \quad X_{34} = \sum_{X_3=1}^{27} \sum_{X_4=1}^{27} X_3 X_4 - n\bar{X}_3 \bar{X}_4;$$

and symmetric entries of the matrix are

$$X_{21} = X_{12}; \quad X_{31} = X_{13}; \quad X_{32} = X_{23}; \quad X_{41} = X_{14}; \quad X_{42} = X_{24}; \quad X_{43} = X_{34}$$

And correlation is given by the relationship:

$$\text{Correlation } (\rho_{ij}) = \frac{\text{Covariance } (X_i, X_j)}{\sqrt{\text{Variance}(X_i) \cdot \text{Variance}(X_j)}}$$

4. Data Presentation and Analysis

4.1. Data presentation

Table 4.1 Data on Energy sum, Quantity of electricity, Tariff rate and VAT

Year	S/N	Energy Sum(₦) (Y_i)	Qty of Energy (kwh) (X_1)	Tariff Rate(₦) (X_2)	VAT (₦) (X_3)
2016	1	952.38	35.1	27.13	47.62
2017	2	952.38	30.79	30.93	47.62
2018	3	1904.76	61.58	30.93	95.24
2018	4	1904.76	61.58	30.93	95.24
2018	5	4761.9	153.96	30.93	238.1
2019	6	1904.76	61.58	30.93	95.24
2019	7	1904.76	61.58	30.93	95.24
2019	8	952.38	30.79	30.93	47.62
2019	9	2857.14	92.37	30.92	142.86
2020	10	4651.16	84.88	54.8	348.84
2020	11	2790.7	50.93	54.8	209.3
2020	12	4651.17	84.88	54.8	348.84
2020	13	5581.4	180.45	30.93	418.6
2020	14	4651.16	81.47	57.09	348.84
2020	15	7441.86	135.8	54.8	558.14
2020	16	4651.16	150.38	30.93	348.84
2020	17	4651.16	150.38	30.93	348.84
2020	18	4651.16	150.38	30.93	348.84
2020	19	2790.7	50.93	54.8	209.3
2021	20	4651	91.4	50.89	348.84
2021	21	2790.7	54.84	50.89	209.3
2021	22	4651.16	95.14	48.89	348.84
2021	23	2790.7	50.74	55	209.3
2021	24	1860.47	33.95	54.8	139.54
2021	25	2790.7	48.88	57.09	209.3
2021	26	930.23	16.29	57.09	69.77
2021	27	3720.93	65.18	57.09	279.07

Source: EEDC Enugu, 2021

Table 4.2. Analysis

S/N	(X ₁)	(X ₂)	(X ₃)	(X ₄)
1	952.38	35.1	27.13	47.62
2	952.38	30.79	30.93	47.62
3	1904.76	61.58	30.93	95.24
4	1904.76	61.58	30.93	95.24
5	4761.9	153.96	30.93	238.1
6	1904.76	61.58	30.93	95.24
7	1904.76	61.58	30.93	95.24
8	952.38	30.79	30.93	47.62
9	2857.14	92.37	30.92	142.86
10	4651.16	84.88	54.8	348.84
11	2790.7	50.93	54.8	209.3
12	4651.17	84.88	54.8	348.84
13	5581.4	180.45	30.93	418.6
14	4651.16	81.47	57.09	348.84
15	7441.86	135.8	54.8	558.14
16	4651.16	150.38	30.93	348.84
17	4651.16	150.38	30.93	348.84
18	4651.16	150.38	30.93	348.84
19	2790.7	50.93	54.8	209.3
20	4651	91.4	50.89	348.84
21	2790.7	54.84	50.89	209.3
22	4651.16	95.14	48.89	348.84
23	2790.7	50.74	55	209.3
24	1860.47	33.95	54.8	139.54
25	2790.7	48.88	57.09	209.3
26	930.23	16.29	57.09	69.77
27	3720.93	65.18	57.09	279.07

Mean vector from the sample data are:

$$\bar{X} = \begin{bmatrix} \bar{X}_1 \\ \bar{X}_2 \\ \bar{X}_3 \\ \bar{X}_4 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 3288.62 \\ 80.23074 \\ 43.00407 \\ 229.8933 \end{bmatrix}$$

The dispersion (variance-covariance) matrix from the sample is:

$$(27-1)S_1^2 = \begin{bmatrix} 72777140 & -7032948 & 3726329 & -2.00E+07 \\ -7032948 & 5285.906 & -89829.4 & -488467 \\ 3726329 & -89829.4 & 3933.066 & -259563 \\ -2.00E+07 & -488467 & -259563 & 474723.47 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$S = \begin{bmatrix} 2799120.769 & -270498 & -143320 & 769230.7692 \\ -270498 & 203.3040769 & -3454.98 & 18787.19231 \\ -143320 & -3454.98 & 151.2718 & 9983.192308 \\ 769230.7692 & 18787.19231 & 9983.192308 & 18258.595 \end{bmatrix}$$

The inverse of the dispersion matrix is:

$$S^{-1} = \begin{bmatrix} 4.82932E-08 & -1.1693E-06 & -2.1E-06 & -3.20541E-07 \\ -1.1693E-06 & 8.93722E-05 & -0.00011 & -1.57625E-05 \\ -2.1E-06 & -0.00011 & 0.000312 & -2.81947E-05 \\ -3.20541E-07 & -1.57625E-05 & -2.81947E-05 & 9.6296E-06 \end{bmatrix}$$

Correlation Test

$$\text{Correlation } (\rho_{ij}) = \frac{\text{Covariance}(X_i, X_j)}{\sqrt{\text{Variance}(X_i) \cdot \text{Variance}(X_j)}}$$

$$\rho_{ij} = \begin{bmatrix} & 1 & 2 & 3 & 4 \\ 1 & 1.0000 & -0.02134 & -0.03844 & -0.00585 \\ 2 & -0.02134 & 1.0000 & -1.95065 & -0.28759 \\ 3 & -0.03844 & -1.95065 & 1.0000 & -0.51441 \\ 4 & -0.00585 & -0.28759 & -0.51441 & 1.0000 \end{bmatrix}$$

That is:

$$\rho_{1,2} = -0.02134; \rho_{1,3} = -0.03844; \rho_{1,4} = -0.00585; \rho_{2,3} = -1.95065;$$

$$\rho_{2,4} = -0.28759; \rho_{3,4} = -0.51441$$

5. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

5.1 Result

We noticed that there is an inverse relationship between the energy sum (that is, expenditures on electricity) and the quantity of electricity (energy) obtained at the given energy sum. This means that as the expenditure on electricity increases, the quantity of electricity decreases with correlation coefficient $\rho_{1,2} = -0.021341$; hence the customers spend more money now to get less of quantity of electricity than it used to be in the past, etc. We also observed that the strength of the relationship was weak as it does not get close to one. Again, we noticed that there is an inverse weak relationship between energy sum and tariff rate

and VAT with values $\rho_{2,3} = -1.95065$ and $\rho_{2,4} = -0.28759$. This means that the quantity of energy obtained keep decreasing while the tariff rate and value added tax keep increasing. This means that the customers will be spending more money to get the same quantity (value) of electricity. Finally, we observed that there is an inverse and relatively strong relationship between the tariff rate and the value added tax with the value $\rho_{3,4} = -0.51441$. The relationship is expected because each of these variables is naturally dependent of the other, even though the overall relationship was weak except for tariff rate and VAT. The closer the correlation coefficient is to one the stronger the relationship and vice versa.

Fig. 1: Graphical presentation of the inverse relationship among the variates

Fig. 2: Graphical presentation of the direct relationship among the variates

5.2 DISCUSSION

In this paper, we analyzed the energy sum; that is, the expenditure made by the users of electricity, and the actual value (quantity of electricity) their money can buy for them. We observed from the study that electricity users spent more money to get the same value (quantity of electricity), and the relationship between these two variables are inverse. That means that as one is increasing, the other is decreasing. The effect of

this is so drastic and a reflection of what Nigerians face generally in the other sectors of the economy. From the study, we also found that tariff rate and value added tax is inversely related to quantity of electricity. This means that both tax and VAT deplete the quantity of electricity that is bought by the customers. The only variables that have direct relationship with each other are tariff rate and value added tax. Both of them move in the same direction. The overall effect of these relationship points to the fact that people spent more in Nigeria now to get

the same value they used to get before. Hence, the cost of living is high and increasing while the standard of living is falling and inflation is at alarming rate.

Competing Interests

There is no competing interest

Authors Contributions

Each author contributed in the preparation of the manuscript, Literature review analysis and presentation of the work.

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